

Synthesis of Hydroxyapatite from Eggshells Through Hydrothermal Process

A. Otabil*, F. Yeboah, Y Hou Gbologah

Department of Materials Engineering, College of Engineering, KNUST, Kumasi-Ghana,

Students: otabiladam@gmail.com, fausti.love54@gmail.com

Supervisor: yongdan.hou@yahoo.com

Abstract

Hydroxyapatite was produced using hydrothermal process by reacting calcined eggshells with diammonium hydrogen phosphate at 100 °C and 110 °C for 2, 4, 6 and 8 hours respectively in which the kinetics of hydroxyapatite formation were determined. The crystalline size, crystallinity and amount of hydroxyapatite produced in each sample were obtained using the X-ray diffractometer. The maximum crystalline sizes ranged from 0.536 – 0.702 nm with the largest size occurring on sample treated for 110 °C for 8 hours. The degree of crystallinity and amount of HA formed increased with time and temperature with the largest crystallinity and amount of hydroxyapatite being 90.7 % and 94.5 % respectively, which occurred on sample treated at 110 °C for 8 hours. The rate constant relates to temperature of hydroxyapatite formation by Arrhenius equation, yielding activation energy of 193 KJ/mol.

Keywords

Hydroxyapatite; Eggshell; Hydrothermal treatment; XRD analysis; Activation energy

Introduction

Synthetic Hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) is a calcium to phosphate based biomaterial with chemical constituents as the natural hard tissue (L. C ´urkovic et al., 2017). Hydroxyapatite (HA) is used for bone fillers to fill bone defects (Rahmi, 2008) and as a coating material for implantation (Haider et al, 2017). The mechanical and microstructure of HA is influenced by the crystallinity, stoichiometry and processing conditions (Fatimah et al., 2014). Therefore, an appropriate method should be chosen for the production of HA to achieve desired application.

Several transformation mechanisms of HA have been proposed by numerous researchers. Using the Johnson-Mehl-Avrami model, the kinetics of HA was described as diffusion of reactants and its fast transformation into HA as a function of temperature and time (Ivankovic et al, 2007). Also, the kinetics and mechanism of HA was considered as a surface controlled process by conversion reaction from octacalcium phosphate (OCP) to amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) to calcium deficient hydroxyapatite (DAP) and HA (Changsheng et al, 2001).

Many equations have been used to describe the kinetics of HA formation. Using Arrhenius Equation, it is desirable to obtain order of reaction so that the right rate equation can be developed for the activation energy to be calculated (Silvertoot et al, 1988). The value of activation energy of HA formation obtained by researchers differ due to the method and sources from which the HA was produced.

An apparent activation energy of 94.4 kJ/mol of HA coatings prepared using electrochemical deposition and post-hydrothermal synthesis in which the Arrhenius equation was used to determine HA formation rate and temperature (Huang, Xu, & Lu, 2000).

Also, an activation energy of 186 ± 15 kJ/mol was determined for the precipitation of HA at pH 7.4 to 8.4 at temperatures ranging from 10 to 40 °C (Silvertoot et al, 1988).

In this work, hydrothermal method was used to produce HA from eggshells. The synthesized HA powder was characterized using XRD and the activation energy was calculated using the Arrhenius Equation.

Methods and Procedures

Raw Materials

The waste eggshells were obtained from Two Sisters Fast Food Joint at Ayeduase, Kumasi-Ghana. The diammonium hydrogen phosphate (NH₄)₂HPO₄ was of analytical grade from Materials Engineering Laboratory.

Raw Eggshell Treatment

1050 g of eggshells were thoroughly washed with tap water to remove the adhesion. The moisture

content was removed by oven (Heraeus, Germany) drying the eggshells at a temperature at 110 °C for 24 hours. The dried eggshells were grinded using the mortar and pestle (Staatlich, Berlin).

Calcination

The grinded eggshells were placed in three open silica crucibles each containing 230 g for a two-stage treatment in an electric furnace (Vecstar, UK). The first stage, the powdered eggshells was heated up to 450 °C for 2 hours at a heating rate of 17 °C/min to destroy organic residues present.

The next stage involved the heating the samples to 900 °C for 2 hours at a heating rate of 15 °C/min. The calcination was carried out to remove chemical water, decompose carbonates and destroy available pathogens. The sample was furnace cooled, pulverized with a pulverizer (Retsch, Germany) and sieved to particle size of 250 µm.

Hydrothermal Synthesis of Sample

20 g of calcined eggshells was added to 75 ml of 2.88 (mol/L) (NH₄)₂HPO₄ aqueous solution according to **Equation 1** below. The mixture was heated in a Teflon lined stainless steel autoclave pressure vessel (Perkin-Elmer, Germany), which was placed on an electric burner (Heidolph, Germany). The temperature inside the autoclave was measured by thermometer (M.S Germany) which was probed into the autoclave. The samples were heated up to 100 °C and 110 °C at a heating rate of 8.33 °C/min and held for 2, 4, 6 and 8 hours respectively.

The samples were sedimentized through solution aging for 12 hours, after the hydrothermal process. The sediments were then washed and

oven dried for 24 hours at 80 °C to remove the moisture. Samples were obtained as white dried powder, which were grinded using the mortar and pestle and sized to particle size of 250 µm.

Analysis

The crystalline phase, structure and size of samples were analyzed using XRD with a CuKα radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) over angle goniometry with 2θ scan from $20.040^\circ - 79.960^\circ$ and $5.025^\circ - 79.975^\circ$ for calcined eggshells and HA respectively. Which were scanned at a speed of

3s with a step size of 0.08 2θ using a voltage of 45 kV and current of 40 mA. The crystalline size was evaluated using the Scherrer equation:

$$\text{Crystalline Size} = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \text{ Equation 2}$$

$\lambda = 0.154 \text{ nm}$ for copper $k\alpha$ and $\beta =$ Full wave half maximum width and $\theta =$ Diffraction angle

Percentage of crystallinity =

$$\frac{\text{crystalline area}}{\text{crystalline area} + \text{amorphous area}} \times 100\% \text{ Equation 3}$$

Results and Discussion

Characterization of Calcined Eggshell

Table 1 Physical Characterization of Calcined Eggshells

Temperature (°C)	Colour	Odour	Softness	Weight (g)	Weight loss (%)
25	gray brown	stink	hard, flake	700	–
900	white	odourless	soft, powder	380	45.71

Physical characterization of eggshells presented in **Table 1**, displays a change in colour from gray brown to white after calcination. This indicates that calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) which is the main component of eggshell has decomposed at 900 °C. The results also showed a change in weight after calcination. The reduction in weight was due to loss of organic compounds which is known to be 4 % (Dennymol P. V, 2014) and the removal of carbonaceous matter contained in the eggshell in this work. The weight of the eggshell sample calcined at 900 °C was reduced by 45.71 % by weight measurement.

The XRD results from **Figure 1** below shows the calcination of the eggshells at 900 °C. The major phases displayed by the peaks are lime (CaO)

(PDF#37-1497) and portlandite (Ca(OH)_2) (PDF#44-1481). The presence of the Ca(OH)_2 may be due to interaction of CaO with water vapour in the air after calcination (Tangboriboon et al, 2012). The sharpest peak of CaO occurred on the (200) plane with a peak width of 0.133° compared to Ca(OH)_2 whose sharpest peak was on the (110) plane with a peak width of 0.612° . CaO displayed a higher quantity of 63.3 % with a cubic crystal system whereas Ca(OH)_2 gave 36.7 % with trigonal system.

Figure 1 XRD results of calcination of eggshell at 900 °C

Hydrothermal Treatments

Figure 2 XRD patterns for samples hydrothermally treated at 100 °C for (a) 2 hours (b) 4 hours and (c) 8 hours

Figure 3 XRD patterns for samples hydrothermally treated at 110 °C for (a) 4 hours (b) 6 hours and (c) 8 hours

The XRD patterns according to **Figure 2 and 3** above, displayed major phases of hydroxyapatite (PDF# 09-0432) with the highest peak displayed on (211) plane and Ca(OH)₂ as the minor phases. The lattice parameters and density of HA formed in all samples matched with the theoretical values (0.6684 and 0.9418 nm for lattice parameter and 3.16 kg/m³ for density) indicating that, HA can be produced using eggshells through hydrothermal process. The crystalline size of the hydrothermally treated samples were calculated using **Equation 2** and the diffraction peaks at 2θ values corresponding to (211), (300), (222), (202) and (213) planes were respectively selected for the crystalline size calculation. From the calculation, the sharpest peak of HA for samples treated for 100 and 110 °C occurred on (213) plane with a maximum crystalline size of 0.536 and 0.702 nm respectively. (213) plane had the maximum crystalline size due to the narrow peak width providing enough planes for complete destructive interference. The percentage crystallinity was determined using **Equation 3**, the highest crystallinity of 90.70 % occurred on hydrothermally treated sample at 110 °C for 8 hours. The crystallinity increased

with increasing temperature due to increase in nuclei growth. From the XRD patterns (**Figure 2 and 3**), calcium hydroxide phase was present in addition to HA which leads to the increase in pH and the reduction of bacteria growth when used for dental composite application (Ansari et al, 2011).

Kinetics of HA Formation

According to the Arrhenius Equation, the reaction rate takes the following form:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K'(1-x)^n \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

$$K = Ae^{-\frac{Ea}{RT}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Where x = HA content, t = reaction time, K = rate constant n = order of reaction Ea = activation energy

T = reaction temperature R = constant A = pre-exponential factor

Taking natural logarithm of both sides of **Equation 4**

$$\ln\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right) = n\ln(1-x) + B \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

Using data from **Figure 4**, The order of reaction

was obtained by plotting $\ln\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)$ against $\ln(1-x)$ as displayed in **Figure 5**. The reaction order (n) was calculated from the slope. The results were 1.86 and 1.67 respectively for samples treated for 100 and 110 °C respectively. Based on the calculation, the reaction may be considered as a second order reaction ($n=2$). The rate constant (K) was calculated using the second order integration of the form:

$$\frac{1}{1-x} = Kt + B \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

The reaction rate constant (K) was obtained as

the slope by plotting $\frac{1}{1-x}$ against t as shown in **Figure 6** below. The results were 0.42 and 2.25 for 100 and 110 °C respectively with an adjustment R^2 value of 0.9.

Equation 5 can be expressed in a linear form by taking natural logarithm of both sides:

$$\ln k = \left(-\frac{Ea}{R}\right)\left(\frac{1}{T}\right) + \ln A \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

The slope of $\ln K$ verse $(1/T)$ gives (Ea/R) in **Figure 7**, from which the activation energy(Ea) was calculated to be 193 kJ/mol.

Figure 4 Effects of temperature and time on the HA content

Figure 6 Determination of activation energy of HA formation by Arrhenius plot

Figure 5 (a) Plot for obtaining reaction order (b) Plot of $(1/1-x)$ against t for 100 and 110 °C

Conclusion

Hydroxyapatite powder has been produced from eggshells through hydrothermal process at 100 and 110 °C for 2, 4, 6 and 8 hours respectively. From the results, the maximum crystalline size, crystallinity and amount of HA formed occurred on the hydrothermally treated sample at 110 °C for 8 hours with a crystalline size of 0.702 nm, 90.7 % degree of crystallinity and 94.5 % of HA formed. This shows that the crystalline size, degree of crystallinity and amount of HA formed increased with temperature and time. The Arrhenius equation was used to link the rate constant and temperature from which the activation energy obtained by calculation was 193 KJ/mol.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to the laboratory technician of Materials Engineering Department, Mr. Felix Ati and Teaching Assistants who helped us in diverse ways. Lastly, our appreciation to Madam Beatrice Aboagye of the University of Ghana (Legon) for her assistance with the XRD characterization.

References

- Adnan Haider, S. H., Sung Soo Han and Inn-Kyu Kang. (2016). Recent advances in the synthesis, functionalization and biomedical applications of hydroxyapatite: a review. *RSC Advances*, 7, 7442-7458. doi: 10.1039/c6ra26124h
- Ansari, M., Naghib, S. M., Moztarzadeh, F., & Salati, A. (2011). Synthesis and characterisation of hydroxyapatite-calcium hydroxide for dental composites. *Ceramics-Silikáty*, 55(2), 123-126.
- Changsheng Liu, Y. H., Wei Shen, Jinghua Cui. (2001). Kinetics of hydroxyapatite precipitation at pH 10 to 11. *Biomaterials*, 22, 301-306. doi: 10.1016/S0142-9612(00)00166-6
- Dennymol P. V, R. J. (2014). Morphological Diversity in Nanohydroxyapatite Synthesized from Waste Egg Shell : Verification and Optimization of Various Synthesis Parameter. *The International Journal Of Science & Technoledge*, 2(6).
- H. Ivankovic, S. O., E. Tkalcec, G. Gallego Ferrer. (2007). Kinetics of Hydroxyapatite Formation from Cuttlefish Bones. *10th ECerS Conf*, 942-947.
- Huang, L.-Y., Xu, K.-W., & Lu, J. (2000). A study of the process and kinetics of electrochemical deposition and the hydrothermal synthesis of hydroxyapatite coatings. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Medicine*, 11(11), 667-673.
- L. C ´urkovic, I. Z mak, S. Kurajica, M. E. Tonkovic ´, Z. S ˇ okc ´ evic ´ , & Renjo, M. M. (2017). From eggshells biowaste to hydroxyapatite biomaterial. 797–802. doi: 10.1002/mawe.201700052
- N. Tangboriboon, R. K., A. Sirivat. (2012). Preparation and properties of calcium oxide from eggshells via calcination. *Materials Science-Poland*, 30(4), 313-322. doi: DOI: 10.2478/s13536-012-0055-7
- Silvertoot, W. P. I. a. j. C. (1988). Kinetics of hydroxyapatite precipitation at pH 7.4 to 8.4. *Geochimica et Coumchimica Acta*, 52, 1883-1893.
- Solihat, R. (2008). Hydrothermal synthesis of hydroxyapatite from eggshell: xrd, ftir and sem-edxa characterization. (bachelor degree), Bogor Agricultural University.

About the Student Authors

Adam Otabil and Faustina Yeboah will graduate in July 2018 with Bsc. (Hons) Materials Engineering from KNUST.

Press Summary

In this work, hydroxyapatite was produced from the reaction of calcined eggshells and diammonium hydrogen phosphate using hydrothermal process. The hydrothermal process was carried out at 100 and 110 °C for 2, 4, 6 and 8 hours respectively. The obtained product was characterized using the XRD from which the crystallinity, crystalline size and amount of HA formed was determined. The maximum crystalline size, crystallinity and amount of HA formed occurred on the hydrothermally treated sample at 110 °C for 8 hours with a crystalline size of 0.702 nm, 90.7 % degree of crystallinity and 94.5 % of HA formed. The product produced in this work can be used for dental composite application due to the calcium hydroxide phase present in addition to HA which leads to the increase in pH and the reduction of bacteria growth. The activation energy determined was 193 kJ/mol using the Arrhenius equation to link the rate constant and temperature.